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THE WEIGHT GAIN BY CAPILLARY ABSORPTION EVOLVES LINEARLY WITH THE FOURTH ROOT OF TIME

Yury Villagrán Zaccardi¹, Natalia Alderete^{1,2}, Ángel Di Maio¹

¹ LEMIT, CONICET, 52 entre 121 y 122 s/n, 1900 La Plata, Argentina, Tel. +54 221 4831141, yuryvillagran@conicet.gov.ar

² Magnel Laboratory for Concrete Research (Ghent University), Technologiepark Zwijnaarde 904, B-9052 Ghent, Belgium.

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ABSTRACT

The literature, including IRAM 1871, defines the capillary absorption coefficient as a coefficient of proportionality between the weight gain by capillary absorption and time^{0.5}. But for cementitious materials this linearity is not such and there are difficulties in its application. The real behaviour evolves with a curve that progressively decreases its slope with $t^{0.5}$. Therefore, IRAM 1871 indicates a conventional method for calculating the coefficient, thus reducing the repeatability of the experimental test. This calculation method seeks to solve a false hypothesis and is therefore arbitrary and artificial. In this work, a linear relationship between capillary absorption weight gain and $t^{0.25}$ is presented as a solution. This new approach allows consideration of particular aspects of cement-based materials that differentiate them from other porous materials. The solution is supported both empirically and theoretically.

INTRODUCTION

Among the most commonly measured transport properties of concrete, and one that also finds numerous applications from empirical correlation with durable performance, is the capillary absorption coefficient (S). This parameter is used as a descriptor of the transport properties of concrete related to different types of environmental aggressiveness, and a low value of S indicates satisfactory properties to ensure an acceptable service life of a concrete structure [1].

Unsaturated concrete placed in direct contact with water absorbs it by capillary action due to the action of the adhesion forces of the water molecules to the pore walls in the concrete. The test method for determining the S of concrete is standardised by IRAM 1871 [2]. There, the experimental procedure is indicated, and as a particularity, the method of calculation of S. Like the literature, IRAM 1871 considers the evolution of the capillary absorption capacity with $t^{0.5}$, and thus calculates the S value.

However, experimental records show a non-linearity of the evolution of the capillary water absorption with $t^{0.5}$. There are several hypotheses to explain this anomaly, yet normative approaches still apply different methods for the "linearisation" of experimental results with $t^{0.5}$. The problem is that these artificial methods reduce the reproducibility and repeatability of the experimental method, as well as induce misrepresentations in the statistics of the experimental results [3]. This implies that although the experimental procedure has an acceptable variability depending on the operator, equipment and number of samples analysed, this variability is increased when calculating S, and its reproducibility is unnecessarily reduced [3-4]. The main reason for the continued use of this linear relationship with $t^{0.5}$ seems to be the confidence in its physical basis, but a closer look suggests that this perception is incorrect.

PHYSICAL-MATHEMATICAL BASIS OF THE $t^{0.5}$ MODEL AND THE PARTICULAR CASE OF CEMENTITIOUS MATERIALS

The consideration of the linear evolution of capillary absorption with $t^{0.5}$ arises from the physical analysis of the phenomenon in porous materials. There are two possible deductions. The older one is due to Lucas-Washburn. In the present work, a more contemporary one based on the modified Darcy equation is used.

The flow of water in porous materials in the unsaturated state (u) is described locally by the extended Darcy Equation (Eq. 1) [5]. Where $K(\theta)$ is the hydraulic conductivity (with θ being the volumetric saturation degree), and F is the capillary force, which is connected to the negative gradient of the capillary potential ψ . Combining Eq. 1 with the continuity equation yields the Richards Equation (Eq. 2). Defining the hydraulic diffusivity function, $D = K(d\psi/d\theta)$, gives Eq. 3 with distance x (1D).

To solve Eq. 3, the Boltzmann transformation ($\phi = x-t-0.5$) is applied defining $\theta = f(\phi)$. Then, it can be written as Eq. 4. With boundary conditions $\theta = \theta_s$ at $\phi = 0$ (saturation at the surface in contact with water) and $\theta = \theta_d$ when $\phi \rightarrow \infty$ (semi-infinite homogeneous and unsaturated medium), the solution is Eq. 5. This last equation shows that as the material absorbs the liquid content versus depth progresses with $t^{0.5}$ maintaining the profile $\phi(\theta)$. When known, the cumulative absorption i is given by Eq. 6 [6], which is the basis of the traditional approach to calculate S.

Considering Eq. 6, IRAM 1871 [2] instructs to calculate a single value of a sector of the experimental curve covering 10 to 90 % of the maximum capillary absorption capacity. This fabricated procedure imposes a convention to solve the problem of non-linearity. However, the process is made more complex by calculating a single value of S for the set of samples rather than individually for each sample. Thus, the outlier elimination criteria decrease the repeatability of the method. The calculation method modifies the statistical distribution of S with respect to the experimental statistical distribution [3-4, 7]. On the other hand, according to the model of Pradhan et al. [8] based on the distribution of pore sizes in concrete, when considering a cylindrical pore structure invariant with time, the capillary absorption should be linear with $t^{0.5}$. Therefore, the non-linearity with $t^{0.5}$ is a reflection of a variable structure.

$$u = K(\theta)F = -K(\theta)\nabla\psi \quad (1) \quad -\frac{\phi}{2} \frac{d\theta}{d\phi} = \frac{d}{d\phi} D \frac{d\theta}{d\phi} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial\theta}{\partial t} = \nabla K(\theta)\nabla\psi \quad (2) \quad x(\theta, t) = \phi(\theta)t^{0.5} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial\theta}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D \frac{\partial\theta}{\partial x} \right) \quad (3) \quad i = t^{0.5} \int_{\theta_d}^{\theta_s} \phi \, d\theta = S \cdot t^{0.5} \quad (6)$$

There is no consensus on the reasons for the deviation from the linear evolution with $t^{0.5}$, and there are several theories (effects of concrete hygroscopicity, gravity, occluded air, heterogeneous moisture distribution, changes in electroviscosity, the chemical composition of the pore liquid, or the contact angle). An analysis of the consistency of

these hypotheses can be found in [9], where the hygroscopicity of the material given by calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H) and its swelling with increasing moisture content is considered to be the most robust.

For this particular case, the swelling of C-S-H has been measured macroscopically [10-11] and microscopically [11-13]. The moisture retention of dry concrete is a clear sign of the non-stationary condition of the capillary absorption phenomenon. The changes in pore structure can be interpreted with a linear evolution with $t^{0.5}$ [9-11], which implies a rate of change fast enough to modify the capillary absorption rate.

Consequently, capillary absorption with anomalous evolution with $t^{0.5}$ is affected by swelling that also evolves with $t^{0.5}$. The combined effect would allow a more complete description of the process.

PHYSICAL-MATHEMATICAL BASIS OF THE PROPOSED MODEL

The effect of C-S-H swelling with moisture content can be translated into a time-varying hydraulic diffusivity coefficient. This concept has been applied to porous materials other than cementitious materials [14-15]. The Richards Equation is considered to have a time-dependent diffusivity (Eq. 7). The diffusivity is defined as a separable function (over γ and δ) of θ and t , according to Eq. 8. With the substitution of variables in Eq. 9, Eq. 7 is rearranged as Eq. 10, with boundary conditions $\theta = \theta_s$ at $x = 0$, $\tau > 0$; $\theta = \theta_d$ at $x > 0$, $\tau = 0$; and $\theta = \theta_d$ at $x \rightarrow \infty$, $\tau > 0$. After the Boltzmann transformation, a solution analogous to Eq. 6 is obtained, according to Eq. 11.

Then, the problem is reduced to define γ in order to consider the evolution of the hydraulic diffusivity. The linear progression of the expansion with $t^{0.5}$ suggests that the expansion occurs only in the zone reached by the capillary absorption front. Swelling causes external expansion but also an increase in tortuosity due to the internal constraint to this deformation. Thomas and Jennings [16] showed that if the degree of constraint (with values $0 = \text{no constraint}$ to $1 = \text{full constraint}$) is greater than the value numerically equivalent to the initial pore volume fraction, the porosity will be reduced due to expansion of one of the material phases. This required restriction is sufficiently low to be compatible with the capillary suction anomaly in cementitious materials. Therefore, considering the hydraulic diffusivity evolution to be proportional to the swelling strain, Eq. 9 becomes $\tau = t^{0.5}$, which means that γ is defined according to Eq. 12. Finally, Eq. 11 expressed in terms of time is Eq. 13, giving theoretical support to the experimental evidence of capillary absorption evolution.

One aspect to highlight is that the proposed approach does not imply any modification of the experimental procedure described in IRAM 1871, but only of the method of analysis of results and calculation of S.

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D(\theta, t) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} \right) \right) \quad (7) \quad i = S^* \cdot \tau^{0.5} \quad (11)$$

$$D(\theta, t) = \gamma(t) \cdot \delta(\theta) \quad (8) \quad \gamma(t) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot t^{-0.5} \quad (12)$$

$$\tau = \int_0^t \gamma(a) da \quad (9) \quad i = S^* \cdot t^{0.25} \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D(\theta) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} \right) \right) \quad (10)$$

FIT OF EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS TO THE $t^{0.25}$ MODEL

From what has been mentioned above, the traditional fit to the linear relationship with $t^{0.5}$ ($S_{0.5}$) can be replaced by a linear fit with $t^{0.25}$ ($S_{0.25}$). For greater reliability of the analysis of the adjustment, this comparison does not include own results but results from other

authors taken from the literature, in particular in the Proceedings of previous Congresses of the Argentinean Association of Concrete Technology, published since 2004, when IRAM 1871 came into force [2]. Figures 1 to 9 show all reported weight gain determinations, with regression lines during the period of dominant capillary rise. A necessary clarification is that the linear relationship extinguishes when the wetting front tends to equilibrium, which stops advancing as a reflection of the extinction of the capillary potential or because the capillary rise height has covered the entire height of the samples. For this reason, the coefficients $S_{0.25}$ were calculated from the experimental results of the first period of the transport phenomenon, while the second period is attributed to a mixed transport phenomenon or other than capillary rise.

Figure 1: Fitting to data in Bolla et al. [17] and Bossini y Anaya [18]. [Translation of axes titles: y-axis: Capillary absorption capacity; x-axis: Time]

Figure 2: Fitting of data in Cabrera et al. [19]. [Translation of axes titles: y-axis: Capillary absorption capacity; x-axis: Time]

Figure 3: Fitting of data in Fernández Luco and Climent [20]. [Translation of axes titles: y-axis: Capillary absorption capacity; x-axis: Time]

Figure 4: Fitting of data in González and Montenegro [21]. [Translation of axes titles: y-axis: Capillary absorption capacity; x-axis: Time]

Figure 5: Fitting of data in Miguel et al [22] and Moro et al [23]. [Translation of axes titles: y-axis: Capillary absorption capacity; x-axis: Time]

Figure 6: Fitting of data in Pique et al [24] and Priano et al [25]. [Translation of axes titles: y-axis: Capillary absorption capacity; x-axis: Time]

Figure 7: Fitting of data in Sacerdote and Rahhal [26]. [Translation of axes titles: y-axis: Capillary absorption capacity; x-axis: Time]

Figure 8: Fitting of data in Señas et al [27] and Bascoy and Colobraro [28]. [Translation of axes titles: y-axis: Capillary absorption capacity; x-axis: Time]

Figure 9: Fitting of data in Mattio et al [29]. [Translation of axes titles: y-axis: Capillary absorption capacity; x-axis: Time]

It is noticeable that in all cases the coefficient of determination remains extremely high. In Figure 10 it can be seen that 81% of the curves analysed showed a coefficient of determination with the linear relationship with $t^{0.25}$ of 0.985 or higher, while for higher coefficients of determination of 0.99 and 0.995 the percentage gradually decreases to 73 and 57 %. Thus, the reliability of the obtained S is very high.

A sensitive aspect is the use of the S value in practice. The Argentinean Regulation CIRSOC 201 [1] sets a limit value of $4 \text{ g/m}^2/\text{s}^{0.5}$ for concrete to be used in structures with durability requirements. This limit is only applicable if the experimental data are analysed with the $t^{0.5}$ approach. From a mathematical point of view, it is feasible to find a relationship between $S_{0.5}$ and $S_{0.25}$, but the method of calculation by convention of $S_{0.5}$ makes the problem not purely mathematical. Figure 11 shows the relationship between the coefficients obtained when considering $t^{0.5}$ and $t^{0.25}$ with the data presented above. The set of values includes 84 mixes, carried out and evaluated by different operators and equipment, following the procedure in IRAM 1871. According to the exponential correlation obtained, the limit of $4 \text{ g/m}^2/\text{s}^{0.5}$ is equivalent to $127 \text{ g/m}^2/\text{s}^{0.25}$. The advantages of using the second value as the limit instead of the first one are its better repeatability and reproducibility and its lower dependence on the number of samples tested and the test duration, all as a consequence of the complete linearity of the experimental results with $t^{0.25}$.

Figure 10: Histogram of distribution of coefficients of determination for the fit with $t^{0.25}$. [Translation of axes titles: y-axis: Frequency; x-axis: Coefficient of determination]

Figure 11: Correlation between $S_{0.25}$ and $S_{0.5}$ for data obtained according to IRAM.

CONCLUSIONS

The anomaly of capillary absorption phenomena in cementitious materials (non-linearity with $t^{0.5}$) has been reported and discussed for quite some time. One possible explanation for continuing to use a linear $t^{0.5}$ law is the lack of a theoretical basis to explain the observed deviation. In this paper an excellent experimental fit to a linear function of $t^{0.25}$ was presented when testing according to IRAM 1871. This solid empirical evidence was supported with a theoretical explanation (C-S-H swelling) and a mathematical model of the transport phenomenon. Furthermore, a consistent equivalence between the coefficients $S_{0.5}$ and $S_{0.25}$ is established. From the analysis of the results in the literature, a correspondence of $127 \text{ g/m}^2/\text{s}^{0.25}$ was obtained for the durability limit value of $4 \text{ g/m}^2/\text{s}^{0.5}$. It should be noted that this new approach does not imply any modification in the experimental method, but simply a modification in the way the data obtained and the calculation of the capillary absorption coefficient are analysed.

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